

Electrocardiographic Changes in Patients Presenting with Acute Stroke: A Myocardial Ischemia Mimic

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Abstract:

Background: Physicians are confronted on having ECG in patients with acute stroke as it can mimic that of myocardial infarction/ischemia. They should be aware of the fact that, these ECG changes are taking place due to acute stroke and not due to myocardial infarction/ischemia.

Objective: The objective of the present study was to study ECG changes in patients with acute stroke.

Methods: A hospital based cross sectional study was carried out for a period of 6 months at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda. A total of 100 patients were included who were eligible for the present study as per the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Detailed history taking, Clinical examinations, vital records, ECG at regular intervals and neuroimaging were done.

Results: Present study showed that the majority of stroke cases (75%) were seen in 51-70 years of age groups. 44 patients with acute stroke in our study showed ECG changes. Out of 44, 16 (80%) of patients with intra-cerebral hemorrhages, 25 (33.78%) of patients with infarct had changes and 3 (50%) of patients with SAH had ECG changes. ST segment and T wave changes were most commonly noted after cerebral hemorrhage.

Conclusions: T wave inversion, left axis deviation along with left ventricular hypertrophy and QT prolongation were common ECG changes in patients with acute stroke.

Keywords: Acute stroke, ECG changes, T wave inversion.

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Introduction

It has been estimated that globally the incidence of acute stroke is around five lakhs. Most of the strokes (acute cerebrovascular episodes) are of two types -the most common is ischemic stroke and the less common type is hemorrhagic stroke. Hemorrhagic stroke can be intra-cerebral or subarachnoid type. The death rate has been estimated to be around 22% of the total cases of acute stroke [1]. ECG changes are commonly found in cases of acute stroke and that too classically found in intra-cerebral hemorrhage type. These changes mimic the changes seen in patients who suffered from myocardial infarction. Coexisting hypertension or simultaneous presence of coronary atherosclerosis is commonly seen in patients with acute stroke which can lead to an abnormal ECG. Associated cardiac disorders like mural thrombus, deep venous thrombosis, myxoma, atrial septal defect, endocarditis in these patients with acute stroke can be a cause for development of decreased

cardiac output, cerebral embolism, heart block and arrhythmias. This poses challenges for the treating doctors as clinical picture and ECG changes arise confusion. They are challenged by ECG picture as they need to distinguish between ECG changes because of acute stroke from that of ischemic heart disease [2]. Almost of the cases with acute stroke can have abnormal ECG changes like T wave abnormalities, ST segment abnormalities, axis deviation, etc. These changes are noticed immediately after an attack of acute stroke. This may be due to “poor neurological function during admission” [3]. Most of the cases have cardiac rhythm abnormalities in initial few days of attack of acute stroke. Most of the abnormalities are not dangerous and they include premature ventricular complex, premature atrial beats, sinus tachycardia, sinus bradycardia etc. Arrhythmia of clinical importance is not so common and can be seen in 1-4% of the patients with acute stroke [4]. Thus,

physicians are in trouble on having ECG in patients with acute stroke as it can mimic that of myocardial infarction/ischemia. They should be aware of these changes taking place in patients with acute stroke and not due to myocardial infarction. Hence our study aims to highlight some common ECG findings in patients presenting with acute stroke.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting: This observational study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences (BMIMS), Pawapuri, Nalanda. This hospital is the single government tertiary care facility hospital in this area covering Nalanda, Nawada, Sheohar and most parts of Gaya district.

Study Design: Our study was a cross-sectional type of observational study based on detailed history and clinical examinations records, ECG at regular intervals, other relevant investigations and neuroimaging.

Study Duration: This study was conducted over a period of 6 months, from January 2024 to June

2024, after approval from the Ethics Committee of the Institute.

Patient Selection: Patient selection was carried out in the Department of Emergency Medicine, BMIMS Pawapuri Nalanda. The study included patients exhibiting clinical features of acute stroke, which were confirmed by further neuroimaging. A total of 100 patients fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with following criteria were included in the study:

1. Patients presenting with acute stroke.
2. Without any known cardiac comorbidity.
3. No history of cardiotoxic drugs.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with the following conditions were excluded from the study:

1. Patients with underlying cardiac diseases.
2. Patients on cardiotoxic drugs.
3. Patients with electrolyte imbalances.
4. Patients with renal and hepatic diseases.

Results

Table 1: Age wise distribution of stroke cases

Age Groups	Number of cases	Percentage
<51 years	7	7%
51- 60 years	32	32%
61-70 years	43	43%
71-80 years	13	13%
>80 years	5	5%

Table 2: Incidence of abnormal ECG findings in the study groups

Type of Stroke	Number of cases	Abnormal ECG	Percentage
Cerebral hemorrhage	20	16	80%
Cerebral infarction	74	25	33.78%
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	6	3	50%

Table 3: Incidence of rhythm disturbances in the study groups

Types of Stroke	Number of cases	Sinus tachycardia	Sinus bradycardia	% of Rhythm disturbances
Cerebral hemorrhage	20	7(35%)	2(10%)	9(45%)
Cerebral infarction	74	9(12.16%)	0(0%)	9(12.16%)
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	6	2(33.33%)	0(0%)	2(33.33%)
Total	100	18%	2%	20%

Table 4: Incidence of axis deviation in the study groups

Types of Stroke		Left axis deviation	Right axis deviation	Axis deviation %
Cerebral hemorrhage	20	9(45%)	0(0%)	9(45%)
Cerebral infarction	74	14(18.92%)	6(8.11%)	20(27.03%)
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	6	2(33.33%)	0(0%)	2(33.33%)
Total	100	25%	6%	31%

Table 5: Incidence of T wave changes in the study groups

Types of Stroke	Number of cases	Tall T wave	T wave inversion	% of T wave changes
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Cerebral hemorrhage	20	2(10%)	8(40%)	10(50%)
Cerebral infarction	74	5(6.76%)	21(28.38%)	26(35.13%)
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	6	0(0%)	2(33.33%)	2(33.33%)
Total	100	7%	31%	38%

Table 6: Incidence of ST- segment changes in the study groups

Types of Stroke	Number of cases	ST depression	ST elevation	ST segment changes %
Cerebral hemorrhage	20	2(10%)	1(5%)	3(15%)
Cerebral infarction	74	6(8.11%)	2(2.70%)	8(10.81%)
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	6	1(16.67%)	0(0%)	1(16.67%)
Total	100	9%	3%	12%

Table 7: Mean values of QT and corrected QT interval in the study groups

Types of Stroke	QT (Mean±SD)	QTC (Mean±SD)
Cerebral hemorrhage	0.4203±0.04	0.453±0.051
Cerebral infarction	0.3712±0.07	0.4370±0.05
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	0.3357±0.045	0.4562±0.14

Figure 1: ECG Showing deep T wave inversion in large intracerebral hemorrhage

Figure 2: ECG Showing cerebral T waves following ischemic stroke

Figure 3: ECG showing ST elevation and QT prolongation in non hemorrhagic stroke

Figure 4: ECG showing LVH and T inversion in subarachnoid hemorrhage patient

Figure 5: ECG findings: marked sinus bradycardia, left bundle branch block and QT prolongation

Figure 6: NCCT Brain showing large cerebral hemorrhage

Figure 7: NCCT Brain and MRI Brain showing cerebral infarction

Our study showed that the majority of cases (75%) were seen in 51-70 years of age groups (Table 1). Out of 100 patients, 20 were presented with cerebral hemorrhage, 74 with cerebral infarction and 6 with subarachnoid hemorrhage (Table 2). Sinus tachycardia was more common than sinus bradycardia in our study, however raised ICP (intracranial pressure) results in bradycardia. Rhythm disturbances were found in 20% of the acute stroke patients: 18% had sinus tachycardia and only 2% had sinus bradycardia (Table 3). Axis deviations were observed in 31% of the cases, 25% cases showed left axis deviation and 6% showed right axis deviation (Table 4). It was most common (45%) in intracerebral hemorrhage. T wave abnormalities were seen in 38% of acute stroke

patients, out of which 31% had T wave inversion and only 7% had Tall T wave (Table 5). ST segment changes were noticed in 12% cases, ST depression (9%) was common than ST elevation. ST segment changes were most commonly (15%) observed after cerebral hemorrhage (Table 6). Significant number of stroke patients showed QT prolongation. (Table 7).

Discussion

Most of the stroke cases are non-hemorrhagic – our study also showed the same incidence (74%). Hemorrhagic cases (ICH 80%, SAH 50%) were associated with ECG abnormalities more than the non-hemorrhagic cases (33.78%). Commonest ECG finding was the T wave inversion, observed in

31% of the acute stroke cases- 40% in ICH, 28.38% in SAH, and 33.33% in non-hemorrhagic group. Next common ECG change was the left axis deviation noticed in 25 % of the cases. LAD were shown by 45% of ICH, 33.33% of SAH and 18.92% of non-hemorrhagic cases. Other common ECG findings were sinus tachycardia (18%) followed by ST depression (9%). There is a mutual causal relationship between cerebrovascular diseases and cardiac disease, this relationship may be explained with brain-heart axis [5]. Dr. Abhilash Somasundaran et al (2015) reported ECG changes in stroke cases, included predominantly T inversions (22.3%) and ST depressions (17.2%) [6]. Mansoureh Togha et al reported in (2013) [7] "ECG abnormalities associated with stroke were T-wave abnormalities, prolonged Q-Tc interval and arrhythmia, which were respectively found in 39.9%, 32.4%, and 27.1% of the stroke patients"

A study performed by Li et al [8] have shown that ST-T segment changes were related to size, site and severity of lesions in acute stroke patients. Therefore, when ischemic ST-T segment changes occur frequently in a patient, all the factors, such as primary cerebral disorders, primary cardiac disorders or other cause-induced cardiac disorders should be considered. According to Frenz and Gormsen (1962) [9] "ECG changes appeared to bear no relationship to arteriographic findings".

In a study Kono and colleagues performed detailed cardiac evaluation of acute subarachnoid hemorrhage patients and stated that ST elevation in the ECG may be due to apical wall motion abnormalities seen on the echocardiogram, but when angiography done, there was no evidence of coronary artery stenosis or coronary artery vasospasm [10].

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